

Article

Climate Change is Risky: Using a Computational Methodology to Relate Corporate Sustainability Reports with their Grades

STAFFORD Marla Royne^{1,*}, KRISHEN Anjala S.², WALTER Dror³, OPHIR Yotam⁴ and HIMELBOIM Itai⁵

¹University of Nevada–Las Vegas, USA; marla.stafford@unlv.edu; <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5978-9331>

²University of Nevada–Las Vegas, USA; anjala.krishen@unlv.edu; <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4749-5130>

³Georgia State University, USA; drorwalter@gsu.edu; <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9870-998X>

⁴University at Buffalo, USA; yotamoph@buffalo.edu; <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5049-7906>

⁵University of Georgia, USA; itai@uga.edu; <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7981-5613>

* Correspondence: marla.stafford@unlv.edu

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Abstract: *Based on stakeholder theory, this study aims to analyze ESG (environmental, social, and governance) reports from sustainable corporations, identify key themes, and investigate their relationship to sustainability grades. The Analysis of Topic Model Networks (ANTMN) approach extracted topics, identified thematic clusters, and mapped their interconnections. Findings indicate that the issues most prominently linked were climate change, climate sustainability, and employee safety; waste and energy did not show correlations. Corporations can therefore interrogate their ESG reports, focusing on key performance indicators and sustainability grades. This research uses a unique methodological approach to understand key topics featured in ESG reports and their relationship with established sustainability grades. Moreover, our results offer novel insight into the communications documents and the link between sustainability and risk.*

Keywords: *Sustainability; ESG, Analysis of Topic Model Networks; Stakeholder Theory; Climate Change; Risk.*

1. Introduction

As the public, governments, and other stakeholders become aware of the impact organizations have on the environment, many organizations voluntarily communicate their performance and influence in environmental, social, and governance (ESG) issues through sustainability reports. While we must recognize that green marketing and corporate sustainability efforts must exist within an institutional framework of sustainability, holding firms responsible by requiring them to report on environmental performance is a step in the right direction. Such reports encompass a wide range of topics and issues that a company chooses to emphasize as crucial to its mission, stakeholders, and consumers. In multiple cross-cultural studies, researchers indicate that ESG reporting serves as a fundamental mechanism for communicating financial transparency and accountability to stakeholders (Oncioiu et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2022). Recognizing that the entire sustainability report is greater than the sum of its issue-specific parts, this study aims to identify the specific topics included in sustainability reports and to explore their interconnectivity in relation to their sustainability grades. These reports then open a window to understanding the context of environmental issues within the larger framework of ESG, providing

insight into managerial communication planning to improve stakeholder perceptions and outcomes. As part of building their conscientious B2B brand, corporations must adopt both short-term and long-term thinking, engage with and empower multiple stakeholder perspectives, and strengthen their network of business relationships (Iglesias et al., 2023; Lochrie, 2016).

To explore these reports and understand how the range of topics included in them is connected, we utilize Stakeholder Theory and Reputation Risk to understand the contents of these reports better and analyze their relationship with their sustainability grades as part of the listing on the Top 100 Sustainable Firms, as determined by Corporate Knights. These grades essentially reflect the company's relative performance compared to its highly sustainable counterparts. This understanding can inform corporations on how to modify both their processes and communications to improve their sustainability grades. In addition to producing environmentally friendly products and targeting green consumers, corporations must develop models of sustainability that incorporate supply chain management and increase the demand for upcycled, recycled, and remanufactured products (Sharma et al., 2010). As such, their ESG reporting would include details on their sustainable efforts, which would later inform their investors and impact their financial performance.

In doing so, this study applies a systematic scope analysis of themes and topics that appear in the corporate sustainability reports of the top 100 sustainable firms. Using topic modelling, a computational method, the dominant issues that companies discuss in their reports are extracted. Applying network analysis, patterns of relationships among these topics, as reflected in content similarities, are identified, leading to overarching themes that capture subsets of topics with content proximity. Patterns of connections and disconnections among topics, this study argues, reflect an organization's perception of how environmental issues align with its sustainability performance and impact, and more generally, with its overall activity. Hence, the primary objective of this study is to identify the key overarching themes and topics prevalent in the sustainability reports of the top 100 sustainable firms.

Communicating ESG activities and plans is essential for organizations to build trust and foster successful relationships with their stakeholders, but it can also be a mere public relations effort. This potential gap can exist between the extent to which organizations report on environmental topics, and more broadly on ESG, and their actual reported activity. Therefore, the second goal of this study is to examine the relationship between ecological and risk topics and sustainability grades. This allows us to explore whether or not the primary issues included in these reports may be a significant factor in the assigned sustainability grade.

2. Background

2.1. Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG)

To communicate value to their stakeholders, firms engage in environmental, social, and corporate governance (ESG) activities, a term rapidly overtaking conversations around corporate social responsibility (CSR), corporate social performance (CSP), and sustainability. Over the past few decades, ESG performance has emerged as a key indicator of stakeholder investment potential. ESG criteria provide a framework designed to link corporations to sustainable behaviour. Specifically, the environmental dimension encompasses the conservation of plants, animals, and nature, the social dimension represents the relationships a firm establishes with individuals, and the governance dimension addresses the internal workings of the corporate structure (Wang et al., 2024). Due to the importance of signaling sustainable behaviours to investors, firms carefully disclose and communicate their ESG performance (Lee et al., 2022).

One stream of academic discussion about ESG reporting focuses on current reporting and metrics for ESG performance signaling; findings show that firms do not adequately reflect their own ESG value, impact, and effectiveness (Aksoy et al., 2022). However, what their stakeholders believe will impact corporate perceptions, thus influencing these well-respected sustainability grades designated by Corporate Knights. To effectively share their ESG plans with relevant stakeholders, firms need to communicate their sustainability challenges and proposed solutions, as well as their goals and benchmark their performance to demonstrate continual improvement. Further, studies indicate that

financial performance and ethical investment are complementary, providing symbiotic benefits for both stakeholders and firms (Lee et al., 2023; Seok et al., 2024).

2.2. Stakeholder Theory and Reputation Risks

Stakeholder Theory offers two perspectives of the relationships between stakeholders and firms, one emerging from a moral and ethical view and the other from a strategic and marketplace view. In its original definition, the theory focused on the moral and ethical perspective, emphasizing the actors affected by corporate actions and their right to information transparency and disclosure (Mitchell et al., 1997). On the other hand, the strategic and marketplace view emphasizes the benefits firms can achieve by considering the criticality of their stakeholder relationships (Freeman, 1984).

Stakeholder Theory argues that a critical tenet of financial success and competitive advantage for corporations is the development of trust-based relationships with stakeholders (Choi & Wang, 2009). Often, firms must balance the conflicting demands of their various stakeholders, which requires a deeper understanding of their network of actors and relationships (Bhattacharya & Korschun, 2008). Corporate social performance, or the positive outcome of corporate social responsibility, can provide numerous marketplace benefits for firms, including higher levels of customer satisfaction and loyalty (Du et al., 2007), as well as goodwill or moral capital (Godfrey et al., 2009). Thus, firms often signal value to stakeholders by enacting corporate social performance initiatives (Brower & Mahajan, 2013).

One potential risk corporations face in communicating with their CSR initiatives is that their documentation is not readily accessible to stakeholders. In effect, a higher ease of processing sustainability reports can lead stakeholders to perceive them as more legitimate (Invernizzi et al., 2022). The risk of this difficulty in perception and understanding is not only an opportunity cost, but also a reputational risk. As noted by Zhou and Wang (2020), reputation risk is not well-defined but broadly encompasses the idea that firms can incur notoriety from stakeholders when they accumulate adverse events; hence, the risk of this loss of reputation must be factored into firm strategies. To counter reputation risk related to ESG, firms must transparently communicate their plans in a manner that fosters the trust and commitment of their stakeholders.

Corporate sustainability reports, then, capture a company's perceptions of its ESG responsibilities, what it considers important to its stakeholders and the public, and its contextual proximity with these considerations. Hence, our first research question asks:

RQ1: What are the key overarching themes and topics identified in the sustainability reports from the top 100 sustainable firms?

Climate Change Risk and Grading Systems

Climate change, a crucial element of sustainability, is inherently linked to risk; in fact, climate change is a risk in its own right. Significantly, the adverse effects or risks of climate change, when communicated through sustainability reports, can trigger corporations to move from discussion to action. The climate change risk perception model (CCRPM) identifies cognitive (knowledge), experiential (emotion and personal experience), and socio-cultural (social norms and value orientations) factors as antecedents (van der Linden, 2015).

Comparing more than five different ESG grading systems in their study, Ortiz-de-Mandojana and Antolín-López (2023) indicate that, amongst several sustainability grading systems, the most common key performance indicators (KPIs) for the environment dimension are energy-related, for the social dimension are health, safety, working conditions, and diversity, and for the governance dimension are risk management, anti-corruption, and ethics. Sustainability ranking systems, also known as commercially developed appraisal instruments (CDAs), provide standardized comparison mechanisms for investors. However, Poveda (2023) cautions that grading developers must account for (1) the need for adaptability in the instruments, (2) utilize scientifically sound processes, and (3) identify and implement stakeholder sustainability vision and performance goals when creating their instruments. That is, not all aspects of the sustainability reports—whether focusing on environmental or risk-related issues—actually serve as a proxy for understanding a company's sustainability efforts and success. In effect, grading systems serve as proxies for evaluating a brand, product, or service (Jena, 2020). When

supply chain partners face a decision on which firms to patronize, they rely on grading systems to reduce cognitive overload and make faster, more efficient decisions based on agreed-upon rankings (e.g., Diaz-Sarachaga & Ariza-Montes, 2022). However, if the grading systems do not accurately reflect the information conveyed in firm-based statements, such as their sustainability/ESG reports, the mismatch could lead to negative backlash and become counterproductive. We therefore pose the following questions:

RQ2: Are the environmental topics identified in the sustainability reports associated with the companies' sustainability grades?

RQ3: Are the risk topics identified in the sustainability reports associated with the companies' sustainability grades?

3. Method

To understand the communications of sustainable business-to-business corporations, we downloaded the sustainability (or ESG) and annual reports of the 100 most sustainable corporations according to the Corporate Knights' list of the Global 100 Most Sustainable Corporations of 2021, for which such information was available. This annual assessment of 100 companies utilizes data from nearly 7,000 public corporations, is based on 23 key performance indicators, and the total revenues for the included firms exceed \$1 billion. (Elijido-Ten & Clarkson 2019; Pal & Jenkins 2014). Only when an ESG or sustainability report was unavailable did we use the annual report, after ensuring that the report included information about the company's sustainability, climate change, or ESG program. A total of 95 reports met the criteria.

The top 100 sustainable firms are determined annually by a composite of metrics developed by Corporate Knights. We utilized the 2021 ranking for this research, and the complete methodology for the 2021 rankings is available here ([Corporate Knights, 2021]). As indicated earlier, the Corporate Knights ranking utilizes 23 key performance indicators (KPI) from various categories. Because the ranking (and subsequent grading) encompasses multiple industry groups, the KPIs are not entirely standardized across the firms. That is, many of the KPIs used depend on the industry. However, several KPIs are utilized across all of the qualifying corporations, including percentage tax paid, pension fund quality, supplier score, non-males in executive management, non-males on boards, racial diversity among executives, racial diversity on the board of directors, paid sick leave, sustainability pay link, sanctions deductions, clean revenue, and clean investment.

To assign specific grades to each company after ranking the corporations, Corporate Knights calculates an overall score as the weighted average percentile rank across the KPI metrics. To create the grades, A+ is awarded to the top company, A is given to those above 75%, A- for 70–75%, B+ for 65–70%, B for 60–65%, B- for 55–60%, C+ for 50–55%, C for 45–50%, C- for 40–45%, D+ for 35–40%, D for 30–35%, and D- for 25–30%. Hence, we must note that even the lowest grades are still reflective of highly sustainable corporations because the grades are only provided for the top 100 most sustainable corporations.

An examination of these top 100 companies indicates they are from six continents, with Europe (including the UK) claiming almost half the companies (46); 33 were from North America, 16 were from Asia, two each were from South America and Australia, and one was from Africa (Scott, 2021). A careful evaluation of the 100 companies reveals that all of them are engaged in B2B marketing, indicating a diverse range of stakeholders across multiple channels

ANTMN Modelling

The Analysis of Topic Model Networks (ANTMN) approach (Walter & Ophir, 2019) was used to analyze the reports. ANTMN is a multi-step approach that includes 1) modelling a topic model, 2) calculating a topic network based on topics' co-occurrence in the sustainability reports, 3) grouping the topics into a set of coherent themes using community detection algorithms, and 4) an in-depth qualitative analysis.

Topic modelling is an unsupervised machine learning method for analyzing textual content (Blei et al., 2003). "Topics" are statistical entities, sets of frequency distributions of words, based on the linguistic

assumption of co-occurrence; that is, words used more frequently in the same documents (here, sustainability reports) are assumed to be associated thematically. In topic models, every word in the corpus has a probability of appearing in each topic, and every document is composed as a mixture of all topics (Grimmer & Stewart, 2013). Topic models are a Bayesian generative approach, in which the model “mimics” the writing process of a given corpus of documents, identifying a set of topics from which the existing corpus could have been created (Blei et al., 2003). Topic modelling is a “bag-of-words” approach, which means that narrative, location in the text, and syntax are not taken into consideration (Wallach, 2006). In this work, we use Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) and Gibbs Sampling (Blei et al., 2003) to model the topics.

Our initial attempt to use complete reports as documents with the 95 reports yielded inaccurate, noisy models. As a solution, since each sustainability report consisted of multiple sections, each dealing with different aspects of the report, we treated each PDF page as an analytical unit in our models. Two companies could not be processed in this manner and were removed, resulting in a final corpus of 93 companies. While this slightly decreased the number of companies, the resulting model was much more cohesive and insightful, providing valuable insights into answering our research questions. Our dataset for analysis consisted of 10,478 pages.

Preprocessing included tokenization and removal of punctuation, symbols, numbers, and URLs. We removed very common tokens (appearing in more than half the documents) and scarce tokens (appearing in less than 0.1% of the papers). To assess the optimal number of topics (k) and optimal hyperparameter (Alpha), we estimated a wide range of models with a k -range of 2–60 topics by “skips” of two, and with varying alpha levels (values ranging from $50/k$ to $1/k$). Based on the fit indicator of perplexity scores, we selected a model with 22 topics and an alpha value of $2/k$.

To best understand and interpret the topics, all authors engaged in a qualitative assessment of the words with the highest loading for each topic, the words that were important and unique to each topic (see Roberts et al., 2014), and the documents most representative of each topic. The third and fourth authors conducted the modeling, while all authors discussed topic labeling. All disagreements and refinements were resolved through mutual discussion, based on qualitative assessments, in-depth reading, and domain expertise. Following standard practices in topic modelling (Walter & Ophir, 2019), four “boilerplate” topics that did not consist of a coherent thematic meaning were removed from analysis.

Figure 1. The Research Process

Finally, for statistical analysis (conducted at the company level), topical loadings for each company were calculated as the average loading across all pages related to that company’s reports, and theme loading was calculated as the sum of these averages. Regression analysis was used to assess the relationships between topics and grades. The whole research process that we followed is presented in Figure 1.

4. Results

RQ1: What are the key overarching themes and topics identified in the sustainability reports from the top 100 sustainable firms?

The 18 topics in the model (see Figure 1), clustered around three overarching themes, Environmental Plus, Risk, and Finance & Value, were identified. As discussed in the Methods section, the interconnectivity within this network, as captured by the edges connecting lines between topics, reflects the rate at which topics tend to co-occur with each other, indicating the strength of topic relationships. An edge's thickness captures co-occurrence strength, with stronger edges indicating a high tendency of co-occurrence. Thus, Figure 2 presents the set of identified topics, along with the structural relationships between them. The labeling, loadings, and top unique words for all 18 topics are presented in Table 1.

Figure 2. Overall Model - Topics and Themes in Corporate Reports

It is interesting to observe that when analysing the companies' sustainability reports, no standalone environmental cluster emerged. The first cluster, named Environmental Plus, captures four specific environmental topics, together with other issues of societal importance. The four environmental-related topics were Waste, Energy, Climate Change, and Climate Sustainability, and based on this cluster, they are discussed together with the topics of Community/Pandemic, Employee Diversity, Health, and Customer Service. Two of the environmental topics, while clearly related, actually capture quite different subjects. Climate Change focuses on a discussion about the negative environmental impact, as in risks to business, investments, and the company's portfolio. In contrast, the Climate Sustainability topic focuses on the responsibility of companies to address environmental challenges, including strategic planning for the future, setting goals, and other related activities.

Table 1. Top Words, Names, Loading, and Themes for the 22 Topics

Topic #	Topic Name	Top 15 Words	Loading	Theme
19	Climate sustainability	sustainable, global, business, impact, climate, goals, environmental, value, world, strategy	0.076	Environmental Plus
11	Energy	energy, emissions, scope, renewable, electricity, carbon, power, consumption, total, data	0.063	Environmental Plus
5	Customer service	customers, customer, products, digital, services, business, technology, solutions, service, data	0.058	Environmental Plus
4	Community & pandemic	support, COVID-, pandemic, health, employees, community, people, communities, also, program	0.056	Environmental Plus
15	Employee diversity	employees, diversity, people, women, inclusion, employee, development, work, leadership, training	0.054	Environmental Plus
10	Climate change	climate, risk, risks, sustainable, change, financial, business, investment, clients, portfolio	0.054	Environmental Plus
8	Waste	water, waste, products, materials, environmental, product, recycling, recycled, packaging, used	0.047	Environmental Plus
16	Health	care, health, Henkel, food, patients, healthcare, production, products, people, packaging	0.031	Environmental Plus
7	Value and assets	assets, financial, value, cash, liabilities, income, interest, fair, group, million	0.062	Finance & Value
21	Management	board, committee, directors, executive, governance, corporate, members, supervisory, director, member	0.036	Finance & Value
18	Annual reports	million, Philips, sales, operating, revenue, financial, income, growth, billion, year	0.036	Finance & Value
6	Financial statements	financial, statements, information, audit, reporting, assurance, internal, consolidated, group, accounting	0.035	Finance & Value
14	Shareholders	shares, Dassault, share, systèmes, company, capital, shareholders, meeting, general, December	0.029	Finance & Value
1	Financial planning	year, performance, plan, march, compensation, remuneration, company, total, benefits, plans	0.027	Finance & Value
3	Reports	approach, governance, index, environmental, reporting, performance, social, data, page, material	0.061	Risk
17	Risk	risk, compliance, risks, business, information, security, internal, employees, policy, ethics	0.06	Risk

22	Suppliers rights	suppliers, rights, human, supply, chain, supplier, business, labor, Lenovo, responsible	0.036	Risk
13	Employee safety	employees, safety, health, number, total, employee, rate, training, occupational, years	0.035	Risk
12	Boilerplate	indices, annual, Iberdrola, information, social, action, non-financial, development, project, programme	0.057	[removed]
20	Artifact Sekisui	- Sekisui, chemical, group, environment, human, group's, business, index, system, touch	0.034	[removed]
2	Artifact Konica Minolta	- Konica, Minolta, fiscal, external, issues, environmental, message, environment, group, social	0.028	[removed]
9	Artifact Nestle	- Nestle, united, Unilever, Europe, sales, limited, Unicredit, whole, retail, states	0.023	[removed]

As noted, statements about the company's stance on and activity related to these environmental issues were discussed in the context of the four other topics within this cluster (Employee Diversity, Customer Service, Health, and Community/Pandemic), which is overall consistent with the social KPIs noted by Ortiz-de-Madojana and Antolin-Lopez (2023). That is, when it comes to reporting on a company's responsible investing, or at least on statements related to it, companies perceive environmental issues as being related to other societal value problems, such as the pandemic, diversity among their employees, and the service they provide to their customers. In summary, this cluster represents an overarching societal issue cluster that encompasses environmental and social topics.

The second cluster, Risk, encompasses a discussion on concerns and challenges related to ESG. This cluster covers the specific topic of 'Risk,' which discusses the need for internal regulations to address various corporate risks, including compliance, policies, ethical conduct, and employee safety concerns, as well as corporate responsibility to suppliers and labor rights, aligning with the governance KPIs identified by Ortiz-de-Madojana and Antolin-Lopez (2023). This cluster is remarkably consistent with the concept of risk that is integrated in the literature on ESG. The third cluster, Finance & Value, encompasses discussions on a company's finance, including the following topics: Value and Assets, Financial Statements, Financial Planning, Annual Reports, Shareholders, and Management. As shown in Figure 2, this cluster is distinct from the other two identified clusters.

Hence, understanding how companies discuss environmental issues is not only based on the context in which they discuss it, but also in the contexts where they do not discuss it. The Finance and Value cluster is entirely disconnected from all environmental-specific topics, suggesting environmental issues are not often discussed within the context of company finance (compared with other problems). In contrast, the second cluster Risk is more connected to environmental topics. The connection between the Risk cluster (e.g., employee safety, suppliers) and the environmental issues from the Environmental Plus cluster suggests that companies perceive the two sets of topics as related and feel the need to include these topics and their relationship within their corporate reporting.

RQ2: Are the environmental topics identified in the sustainability reports associated with the companies' sustainability grades?

To address this question, we examined the relationship between environmental topic salience and the overall grades assigned by Corporate Knights. The Climate Change topic was found to be negatively correlated with overall grade ($B = -4.49$, $SE = 1.85$, $p = .017$; adjusted r -squared = .05). (See Figure 3). Specifically, companies with lower overall sustainability grades included more discussion about this particular topic in their reports. Climate sustainability, on the other hand, was significantly correlated with the overall grade, but in a curvilinear way as can be seen in Figure 4 ($B = 82.196$, $SE = 23.70$, $p < .001$; adjusted r -squared = .12). Up to a certain level of salience, focusing more on this topic decreased

performance (grade), but then more emphasis was related to better environmental performance. That is, highly graded companies either discussed climate sustainability extensively or not at all. The Waste and Energy topics were not significantly correlated with the overall grade. The regression in which both topics serve as predictors explained 14.2% of the variability in the dependent variable (overall grade).

Figure 3. Correlation between Climate Change Topic Loadings and Sustainability Grade

Note. The Y axis represents the sustainability grade (1 = D grade and 11 = A+), and topics demonstrate linear predictions in blue and curvilinear ones in red.

Figure 4. Correlation between Climate Sustainability Topic Loadings and Sustainability Grade

Note. The Y axis represents the sustainability grade (1 = D grade and 11 = A+), and topics demonstrate linear predictions in blue and curvilinear ones in red.

RQ3: Are the Risk topics identified in the sustainability annual reports associated with the companies' sustainability grades?

Only one significant relationship was found between any of the Risk-related topics and the sustainability grade: Employee Safety (see Figure 5). The more a company includes discussion about Employee Safety, the higher its sustainability grade ($B = 13.23$, $SE = 4.88$, $p < .01$; adjusted R-squared = .06). For thoroughness and to confirm the lack of a relationship between the Finance & Value cluster (as indicated by the distance in the model), we analyzed the sustainability grade. Neither model was significant ($p > .05$).

Figure 5. Correlation between Employee Safety Topic Loadings and Sustainability Grade

Note. The Y axis represents the sustainability grade (1 = D grade and 11 = A+), and topics demonstrate linear predictions in blue and curvilinear ones in red.

5. Discussion and Implications

Sustainability reports capture how companies and corporations approach sustainability issues and communicate their ESG-related principles, efforts, and impact to their various stakeholders and the general public. This study implements a computational approach to map the topics and themes that emerge in these reports, the contextual relationship among these topics, and their association with companies' sustainability grades.

5.1. Themes, Topics and Context

Interestingly, environmental issues, waste, Energy, Climate Change, and climate sustainability, did not form a distinct cluster, but were discussed alongside the topics of Community/Pandemic, Employee Diversity, Health, and Customer Service. This suggests that, overall, companies associate environmental issues with a broader theme of societal concerns, supporting the notion that companies recognize the environment as a significant social issue that cannot be considered in isolation, but rather in conjunction with other key societal issues. In fact, this aligns with the moral and ethical perspective of stakeholder theory, which holds that the firm has an overall moral and ethical duty to engage in environmental initiatives that support its customers. Moreover, in selecting the top 100 sustainable firms, Corporate Knights indicates that new KPIs utilized in the selection process for 2021 included

how companies were addressing specific social concerns raised in the previous year by the pandemic and the Black Lives Matter movement; at least one of those new KPIs relates to diversity (Scott, 2021), and our topic findings reveal that this issue is indeed part of the company's reporting efforts. However, despite the identification of this topic in our results, the lack of a significant relationship between Employee Diversity and final grade poses an interesting dilemma for these companies.

Further, our results revealed the interconnectedness between the Environmental Plus and Risk clusters, indicating that sustainability is perceived within the context of risk, such as employee safety, rather than solely in terms of financial gain. Supporting this is the finding that environmental issues are not discussed overall in the context of a company's finances; this reinforces the notion that such issues are considered a company's societal responsibility. It is also possible, however, that companies engage in environmental activities as preemptive measures to avoid federal or state regulations or meet public relations goals rather than an activity that impacts the company's "bottom line." As such, our results indicate the need for companies to report on the Environmental Plus/Risk interconnectedness, as well as both the moral/ethical and strategic/marketplace Stakeholder Theory perspectives, in their stakeholder communications. This has the potential to impact stakeholder perceptions regarding the company's operations and financial performance, particularly in relation to its sustainability activities. The close association between environmental and risk topics corresponds to the importance of environmental risk perceptions for climate change action, or the lack thereof.

5.2. Sustainability Topics and Grades

These findings suggest a complex relationship between how companies discuss environmental issues and their overall sustainability grade. Two of the environmental topics, Waste and Energy, showed no significant association with grade. In contrast, Climate Change was negatively associated with grades, indicating that companies with lower overall grades discussed this topic more frequently. This suggests that specific discussions about climate change do not contribute to a higher grade for a company, relative to its peers. In fact, Employee Safety as a Risk topic seems to play more of a role in a company's grade than Climate Change.

However, Climate Sustainability was overall correlated with the sustainability grade, but in a curvilinear way. Up to a certain level of salience, focusing more on this topic decreased performance (grade), but then more emphasis was related to better environmental performance. In other words, highly graded companies either discussed this topic extensively or very little, while middle-level companies exhibited moderate discussions about climate sustainability. The difference between findings related to climate change and climate sustainability is interesting and can be best explained by understanding the important differences between these two seemingly similar topics. As noted earlier, the Climate Change topic focuses on the negative impact of environmental issues. It is possible that companies that discuss Climate Change considerably are simply trying to be seen as environmentally friendly, even if their actual performance is not as strong. One might even consider this a form of Greenwashing that is often present in marketing communications and has the potential to create negative responses among stakeholders. Greenwashing tactics target environmentally conscious consumers, but do not initiate environmental activities that produce real change (Szabo & Webster, 2021).

In contrast, the Climate Sustainability topic focuses on the responsibility of companies to address environmental challenges. The curvilinear relationship of this topic with grades is intriguing. It is expected that companies with middle-level sustainability grades will also exhibit middle-level salience of Climate Sustainability, the topic that captures a company's actions addressing environmental issues. The question is, why would high salience of the topic be captured by companies with both high and low grades? Companies with low grades may seek to highlight their efforts to address sustainability issues, aiming to improve their grades. In contrast, companies with high grades have numerous climate sustainability efforts to showcase.

As discussed, Stakeholder Theory argues for the importance of trust-based relationships with stakeholders (Choi & Wang, 2009). The gap between the level of emphasis on individual environmental issues in the reports and their final grades raises concerns about companies' reputations, as reports may be perceived as not accurately representing a company's actual standings. We suggest that companies at the lower end of sustainability grades consider the connections between their environmental efforts

and financial performance. Currently, the gap between the economic value of a company and sustainability issues is bridged by topics associated with risk. That is, the connection between a company's financial and environmental aspects is connected by concerns and negativity, as suggested by the Risk topics. We also recommend that companies seeking to improve their sustainability grades consider the positive correlation between sustainability efforts and financial gain. Because many stakeholders are concerned with the company's economic health (e.g., shareholders), a stronger connection between these two topics will likely influence reputation risk and the ultimate sustainability grade, which can impact the company's bottom line.

5.3. Methodological Implications

The computational approach proposed in this study makes a methodological contribution in two significant ways. First, rather than searching for a predetermined set of issues, we utilize Topic Modelling to identify naturally emerging topics. Secondly, this approach acknowledges that individual ESG topics are discussed not in isolation, but relative to others. By approaching sustainability reports as a network of interconnected issues, where connections are based on similarities of unique keywords, we can comprehend the context in which different sustainability topics are reported, and more broadly, how companies perceive ESG.

6. Limitations and Future Research

To our knowledge, this is the first paper to use the ANTMN methodology in a rigorous examination of the corporate sustainability reports provided by the top 100 sustainable firms identified by Corporate Knights. Our findings offer significant implications for both the top 100 firms and those companies aspiring to be recognized for their sustainable performance. In summary, our results provide insight into the topics that companies are reporting, as well as those related to higher grades.

However, limitations of our study must be identified. First, our work examined the reports of only the top 100 sustainable companies; therefore, our results are based solely on that information. It is possible that the companies failed to report all activities related to sustainability and climate issues, as well as community and societal-based topics, perhaps because some of their efforts were not fully implemented or did not yield the desired results. Moreover, because of the nature of the Corporate Knights list itself, the variation among the companies may be limited.

Further, because a few companies did not produce an actual sustainability or ESG report, the information provided in the annual report we used may be limited. Hence, future research should expand the sample to include an extensive range of companies that produce sustainability reports. This will allow for research examining a more diverse group of companies, with likely much more variation that will provide expanded insight. Additionally, research focusing on specific industries might be helpful for companies in those industries. Given recent findings that digital and non-digital firms may have varied ESG performance (Jin et al., 2024), this type of research may be fruitful.

Finally, as artificial intelligence (AI) technologies revolutionize B2B knowledge management, strategic decision-making processes, and stakeholder relationships, future research should investigate their impact on ESG grades and sustainability reports (Bag et al., 2021; Petrescu et al., 2022).

7. Contributions and Conclusions

We contribute to the environmental marketing literature in several ways. First, we provide a novel methodology for studying sustainable corporations and their communications, which enables us to analyze the specific content of sustainable reports. Second, our conceptualization of ESG, stakeholder theory, climate change risk, and reputation risk as layered phenomena is unique. As shown in previous research, stakeholders must be informed about corporate sustainability metrics presented in ESG reports. Likewise, companies risk losing their reputations as sustainable corporations if they receive low grades, even after qualifying as such. As such, our results provide insights to marketing and sustainability managers regarding key terms and communication targets for ESG reporting.

Third, we show that while branding themselves as sustainable corporations is an important goal for corporations, they risk being downgraded in critical rankings and thereby overlooked by investors when

their reports do not address important KPIs. Specifically, the topics with the most prominent links to sustainability grades were climate change, climate sustainability, and employee safety. On the other hand, terms such as "waste" and "energy" did not show correlations with sustainability grades. Hence, corporations can utilize our findings to interrogate their ESG reports with an eye on the KPI metrics and the sustainability grades, another contribution of our work centres on the peripheral information we uncovered during our inquiry. Grades and other metrics for sustainable corporations serve as essential guides to investors who are pressed for time to make critical decisions. For example, Pacelli, Pampurini, and Quaranta (2023) found the importance of ESG in selecting asset portfolios, while Sandberg et al. (2023) reported that higher ESG grades are correlated with stronger financial performance. According to the Corporate Knights ranking we utilized, sustainable corporations are also expected to embody innovative mindsets, such as setting high targets for gender and racial diversity in executive management. As such, marketing managers of sustainable corporations must incorporate diversity, equity, and fairness as key pillars not only in their reporting mechanisms but also in their strategic planning activities and overall missions.

As sustainability and climate change remain of considerable importance to organizations, companies are seeking the best ways to not only improve in these areas, but also to communicate their efforts to their stakeholders. For example, sustainable brand positioning is an antecedent to critical relationship outcomes, such as willingness to pay, which is mediated by both calculative and affective commitment (Casidy & Lie, 2023). Hence, our findings have critical implications for all companies and, in particular, those organizations that 1) wish to remain a top 100 sustainable company; 2) want to increase their grade among their peers; and 3) seek inclusion on the Corporate Knights list. In summary, our findings demonstrate that sustainability reports are strategically written forms of corporate communication, representing what companies want others to think about them beyond what they do and who they are.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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